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SATELLITE IMAGERY FOR DOCUMENTING ANCIENT AND HISTORIC MOVEMENT: CASE STUDIES FROM SYRIA, IRAQ, AND UKRAINE

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СУПУТНИКОВІ ЗНІМКИ ДЛЯ ДОКУМЕНТУВАННЯ ДАВНІХ І ІСТОРИЧНИХ ПЕРЕМІЩЕНЬ: ПРИКЛАДИ ІЗ СИРІЇ, ІРАКУ ТА УКРАЇНИ

This article explores the potential of satellite imagery for documenting ancient and historic movement through erosional features known as hollow ways. Based on three regional case studies – southern Ukraine, northern Syria, and southern Iraq – a comparative analysis was conducted using historical satellite images (Corona, Hexagon) and modern imagery from Google Earth. It was found that even a single historical image can reveal more traces of movement than the full catalog of modern imagery. At the same time, each source captures unique segments.

Keywords: satellite imagery, historical imagery, hollow ways, Syria, Iraq, Ukraine.

У статті досліджено потенціал супутникових знімків для документування давніх і історичних переміщень за ерозійними утвореннями, відомими як «дороги-улоговини». На основі трьох регіональних досліджень – Південна Україна, Північна Сирія та Південний Ірак – проведено порівняльний аналіз історичних супутникових зображень (Corona, Hexagon) і сучасних знімків із Google Earth. Встановлено, що навіть один історичний знімок може виявити більше слідів переміщень, ніж повний каталог сучасних зображень. Водночас кожне джерело фіксує унікальні сегменти.

Ключові слова: супутникова зйомка, історичні знімки, давні шляхи, Сирія, Ірак, Україна.

Introduction

In many parts of the world, archaeologists have access to a wealth of high and very high-resolution satellite imagery that record the archaeological landscape from the early 1960s onwards. Early satellite imagery from the 1960s through the 1980s (e. g. Corona, Hexagon) was recorded on film, producing images that allow analysts to discern features only 2–3 metres in size. While 21st century, commercially-available, very high-resolution satellite imagery provides a record of the same landscape with a spatial resolution of 30–50 centimetres, displayed freely in various online platforms and applications.

Intuitively, higher resolution imagery should yield better results for documenting archaeological features in the landscape. On the contrary, all archaeologists learn the impact of various taphonomic processes on the preservation of the archaeological record (Schiffer, 1987), so perhaps sufficiently high resolution, historic imagery should

provide a more complete record since these images show the landscape as it was prior to any damage in intervening years. This study examines this question specifically within the context of documenting the archaeological record of past people movement.

As people move across the landscape, they leave footprints and / or tracks. It is only on paved surfaces that these traces of movement are obscured. Occasionally, footprints are preserved in the archaeological record where they preserve numerous physical and behavioural data about the people who made them (Bell, 2020; Bennett & Reynolds, 2021; Burns, 2021; Hatala et al., 2016; Leary, 2014). More commonly, the past movement of people is preserved in the archaeological record en masse, as lines in the landscape called hollow ways that are formed by innumerable individuals travelling the same route and eroding the ground. Such hollow ways have been documented in the UK, across western Europe, southwest Asia, and Ukraine with further examples known elsewhere (Bell, 2020; Jotheri et al., 2019;

Kariaka, 2022; Kirchner et al., 2020; Scollar, 1957; Sheets, 2009; Ur, 2003, 2010a; Wilkinson, 1993, 2003).

This study focuses on the use of satellite imagery for documenting ancient and historic movement from hollow ways in three unique case study regions: southern Ukraine, northern Syria, and southern Iraq (Fig. 1). The three case study regions all represent unique environments: southern Ukraine is temperate, northern Syria is an arid environment, and the selected area of southern Iraq corresponds to marshland. In all three case study regions, hollow ways were mapped twice: once using historic satellite imagery and a second time using modern, very high-resolution satellite imagery available in Google Earth. This double-mapping process enables direct comparison between the two datasets of satellite imagery and allows for a critical evaluation of the data sources most commonly used to document ancient and historic movement.

The Formation of Hollow Ways

Like other broad categories of archaeological features (e. g. settlements), the physical characteristics of hollow ways, including their precise size and shape, vary both by region and within regions. This variation is due to both physical and cultural processes responsible for the formation of hollow ways.

Physically, hollow ways are linear features initially formed by the erosion of soil caused the traction of people and/or animals moving by foot (Jotheri et al., 2019; Wilkinson et al., 2010), wheeled vehicles (Raccidi, 2013), and even boats (Jotheri et al., 2019). Once formed, the linear depression of hollow ways can capture water run-off, causing further erosion and even the formation of deep gullies in more temperate and tropical regions of the world (Bell et al., 2020, pp. 1–3; McClellan & Porter, 1995; Sheets, 2009, pp. 163–165; Wilkinson et al., 2010).

Fig. 1. We compare historic and very high-resolution satellite imagery for documenting hollow ways in three case study regions: southern Ukraine, northern Syria, and southern Iraq (Background: ESRI World Topo)

This process of erosion through use and erosion from water run-off can alternate for centuries until a hollow way is abandoned and begins to gradually fill in with sediment (Wilkinson et al., 2010).

When an archaeologist excavates a hollow way, they are excavating the fill and, therefore, any dating evidence collected at the base of a hollow way cut only represents a *terminus ante quem*, the latest date the hollow way was in use (Wilkinson et al., 2010; Wilkinson, 2003, pp. 111–120). More commonly, hollow ways are dated by association to the site(s) they are connected to (Casana, 2013; Jotheri et al., 2019; Ur, 2010b; Wilkinson & Tucker, 1995). For example, if a hollow way connects two Bronze Age sites, then the hollow way is considered to also date to the Bronze Age. Of course, it follows that hollow ways, like sites, can date to multiple time periods.

Hollow ways are mainly found in connection to sites, often forming a radial pattern of lines around a site (Wilkinson, 2003, pp. 111–120). Since hollow ways are erosional features, their precise shape is determined by the route choices of the people and / or animals responsible for their formation and continued use (Jotheri et al., 2019; Wilkinson, 2003, pp. 111–120). For this reason, hollow ways are a type of archaeological trace fossil that record human movement and travel behaviours on a population scale, providing a unique insight into past cultures.

The Hollow Ways of Iraq and Northern Syria

Hollow ways in this region were first observed and documented in northern Syria during the 1930s using aerial imagery (Poidebard, 1934) and have continued to be mapped using both aerial images and, since the 1990s, with satellite imagery (Altaweel & Hauser, 2004; Jotheri et al., 2019; Stone, 2020; Ur, 2010a, 2010b, 2002; van Liere & Lauffray, 1954; Wilkinson, 1993; Wilkinson & Tucker, 1995). Cumulatively, more than 12,000 hollow way segments have been mapped across Iraq and northern Syria, creating an important record that have been used to study traffic patterns and the social networks behind them over time (Jotheri et al., 2019; de Gruchy, 2017a; Priß et al., 2025; Ur, 2010a, 2010b; Wilkinson, 2003; Wilkinson & Tucker, 1995).

In northern Iraq and northern Syria, hollow ways most commonly appear in aerial and satellite imagery as dark lines with bright edges (Ur, 2009; Wilkinson et al., 2010). In this arid environment, the darkness of the middle of a hollow way corresponds to increased moisture and vegetation relative to the

surrounding landscape, while the bright edges appear due to the formation of calcium carbonates when moisture evaporates from the sloped sides (Wilkinson et al., 2010).

In southern Iraq, the hollow ways can also appear as dark lines due to increased moisture and vegetation; however, they can also appear as bright lines. The sometimes-bright appearance of hollow ways in southern Iraq occurs when their fill contains large quantities of shells in a context of dark, dried marsh soils (Fig. 2).

In the Orontes Valley of northern Syria, hollow ways are typically less than 15 metres wide (Casana, 2013, p. 263). Further east, in the Jazira region that spans the area from the Khabur valley of northern Syria to the Euphrates river in northern Iraq, hollow ways are typically much wider, often measuring 70–120 metres wide, but later Sassanian–Early Islamic hollow ways tend to be narrower (Ur, 2010b, p. 82; Wilkinson et al., 2010). South of Baghdad, the hollow ways of southern Iraq are much narrower at only 2–5 meters wide (Jotheri et al., 2019, p. 10). While in the adjacent Khuzestan region of southwestern Iran, hollow ways are often 40–60 metres wide (Casana, 2013, p. 264).

Despite their size, hollow ways across the entire region typically have a surface depth of less than 50 centimetres (Altaweel & Hauser, 2004; Casana, 2013; Jotheri et al., 2019; Wilkinson, 2003; Wilkinson et al., 2010; Wilkinson & Tucker, 1995, p. 24). This relatively shallow depth across such a large feature can make hollow ways difficult to identify on the ground without the aid of aerial or satellite imagery.

There is dating evidence from excavation that the oldest hollow ways in northern Syria date to at least the early third millennium B.C. (Wilkinson et al., 2010, pp. 762–63), and there is additional evidence suggesting some hollow ways in northern Syria and both northern and southern Iraq date to the early fourth millennium B.C. (de Gruchy, 2017a; Jotheri et al., 2019; Ur, 2010b, pp. 133–146). Across the region, there are hollow ways that date to all intervening time periods up to the present day. One of the newest hollow ways documented formed between 2009 and 2012 near the archaeological site of Carchemesh on the Turkish-Syrian border, which corresponds to the outbreak of the Syrian civil war in 2011 and the mass movement of refugees from Syria into Turkey (de Gruchy & Cunliffe, 2020, p. 124).

Fig. 2. A hollow way located on dark, desertified marsh soils in Thi Qar province, Iraq, filled with light sediment with large quantities of sunbleached shells (Photos: Michelle de Gruchy 2022)

The Hollow Ways of Southern Ukraine

The topic of steppe routes on the territory of Ukraine has only recently begun to be studied. The first mentions of the possibility of identifying and mapping ancient hollow ways date back to Kostiantyn Shyshkin, who considered them a specific type of archaeological site that remained insufficiently explored (Shyshkin, 1964, pp. 199, 203–204; 1966, pp. 116, 119). However, the researcher merely pointed out this possibility, and it did not receive further development in subsequent publications. Nevertheless, his drawings based on aerial photography studies include markings of ancient hollow ways (Shyshkin, 1964, figs. 1, 2, 4; 1966, figs. 1, 2). Due to the lack of access to aerial and satellite imagery, this topic did not advance further domestically.

In our 2021 research, we conducted the first large-scale mapping of specific regions with concentrations of ancient hollow ways and associated burial mounds – namely, the region of the Scythian royal barrow of Ohuz (between the Dnipro and

Molochna rivers) (Boltryk & Kariaka, 2021, pp. 199–214), and part of the steppe between the modern settlements of Davydiv Brid and Beryslav (between the Dnipro and Inhulets rivers) in Kherson Oblast (Kariaka, 2021, pp. 169–184). The main goal of these studies was to show the close spatial relationship between burial mounds and ancient hollow ways.

The study of ancient communication routes using remote sensing methods in southern Ukraine has certain specific features. Through meticulous mapping, we traced the general directions of connections between regions and microregions. In the open steppe landscapes, ancient burial mounds served as key landmarks. In the vast majority of cases, the hollow ways were oriented toward individual mounds or their clusters. At the same time, the identified hollow ways networks illustrate numerous interconnections and movement possibilities between different areas, but for various reasons, most of them are not associated with known archaeological sites. This presents a significant problem — the lack of dating. The burial mounds

associated with the hollow ways generally have a wide chronological range – from the Eneolithic to the medieval period – although Bronze Age and Scythian-period mounds are the most typical. The absence of links to excavated and dated sites also leaves unresolved the question of the function and purpose of the identified ancient hollow ways.

It is important to emphasize that these hollow ways are not connected to known historical communication lines preserved on 19th-century maps (Kariaka, 2021, p. 174). In some cases, a small portion of the communication lines we studied in the deeper steppe areas were associated with crossings of ravines and streams as natural obstacles. Therefore, we consider the development of this particular direction – the study of ancient hollow ways systems in the steppe Dnieper region – to be especially promising.

Methodology

The dataset used for northern Syria is updated from an earlier, unpublished dataset for a report assessing damage to heritage in Syria (de Gruchy, 2017b). The five sites are all located in the Jazira region of northern Syria and were originally selected for the purposes of this unpublished report. The earlier dataset of hollow ways around these five sites was produced by mapping the hollow ways around each of the five sites using historic Corona imagery, then mapping the same features entirely again using very high-resolution imagery available in Google Earth. This second map of hollow ways has been updated for this study to include features visible in more recent very high-resolution satellite imagery available in Google Earth eight years later.

For southern Iraq, we used a portion of a pre-existing dataset of hollow ways mapped using very high-resolution imagery available in Google Earth in 2018 that were systematically ground-checked and

published in 2019 (Jotheri et al., 2019). The portion selected corresponds to a location within the marshes where Corona imagery is readily available. The pre-existing dataset of hollow ways was updated using more recent very high-resolution satellite imagery that has become available over the last seven years; then the hollow ways were mapped a second time with historic, Corona imagery.

In Ukraine, an attempt to study in more detail the phenomenon of ancient hollow ways visible in satellite images was aimed at also clarifying the specifics of their use in areas where natural barriers were overcome. Against the general background, they mostly appear as darker lines approximately 10–15 meters wide. Nearly all of them are spatially aligned with large burial mounds or mound clusters, which served as markers for major routes across the steppe. Particularly those associated with crossings of watercourses – we selected a region east of the modern city of Vasylivka in Zaporizhzhia Oblast, specifically the lower reaches of the steppe river Karachekrak. In the studied section, this river flows westward toward the Kakhovka Reservoir – historically known as the Great Meadow (Velykyi Luh).

The area we examined extends approximately 12 kilometers and contains a significant concentration of ancient hollow ways remnants. On its eastern side, the territory is bounded by a wide network of ravines and streams – namely the Lelykhova, Shyroka, and Zynevata ravines.

Hollow ways were mapped in all three case study areas twice: once using historic Corona or Hexagon satellite imagery and a second time using very high-resolution satellite imagery available in Google Earth (Tab. 1). All available very high-resolution imagery was used to create maps of hollow ways visible from this data source.

Table 1. Imagery used to compare documenting hollow ways using historic satellite imagery and very high-resolution satellite imagery available in Google Earth

Case Study Area	Historic Imagery	Google Earth Imagery
Northern Syria	December 1967 November 1968 (Corona)	2004–2024
Southern Iraq	January 1968 (Corona)	2009–2024
Southern Ukraine	July 1972 (Hexagon)	2004–2022

Next, the total length of hollow ways segments mapped within each case study area by data source (historic or Google Earth) was calculated as an initial measure for quantifying and comparing the relative visibility of these features.

Finally, in each case study area, the quantity of hollow ways uniquely visible in a single dataset (historic or Google Earth) were estimated by selecting segments in each dataset that do not intersect the other. The total lengths of these selected segments provides an approximation of the volume of data that would be missed if a researcher used only one dataset or another to map hollow ways. It is not an exact number, because segments from the historic and Google Earth datasets that closely parallel each other without touching will be counted; while segments of hollow ways in one dataset that cross segments in the other dataset will not be counted (Fig. 3).

Results

In the northern Syria and southern Iraq case study areas, the presence of hollow ways is established. In the southern Ukraine case study area, the remnants of ancient hollow ways identified and documented for this study exhibit a typical appearance previously described in earlier publications (Fig. 4) (Boltryk & Kariaka 2021; Kariaka, 2021).

Across all three datasets, the value of even a single strip of historic satellite imagery for documenting hollow ways is evident when results are compared to the entire catalogue of very high-resolution satellite imagery available in Google Earth for each case study area (Tab. 2). In northern Syria and southern Iraq, each Corona imagery allowed for the mapping of more lengths of hollow ways than the full volume of very high-resolution satellite imagery

Table 2. The total length of hollow ways documented in each case study area listed by source

Case Study	Data Source	Hollow Ways (total length, m)
Northern Syria	Corona 1967	133,757
	Corona 1968	221,688
	Google Earth, 2004–2024	113,779
Southern Iraq	Corona 1968	224,909
	Google Earth, 2009–2024	132,607
Southern Ukraine	Hexagon 1972	63,447
	Google Earth, 2004–2022	65,875

available on Google Earth combined. In southern Ukraine, the Hexagon imagery and the combined catalog of all very high-resolution satellite imagery available in Google Earth allowed for similar lengths of hollow ways to be mapped.

Nonetheless, further examination reveals that modern very high resolution satellite imagery can detect hollow ways that may not be visible in historic

imagery. The values presented in table 3 should be taken as estimates only, rather than precise values. Nonetheless it is clear that each data source used in this study allowed for the unique mapping of a relatively large amount of hollow ways (Tab. 3). This is further supported by visual comparison of the different datasets in each of the three case study areas (Fig. 5).

Table 3. The estimated total length of unique hollow ways documented in each source listed by case study area. In Northern Syria, the values for the Corona imagery represent the hollow way segments unique to that set of imagery (e.g. the hollow ways that are visible only in Corona 1967, not Corona 1968 nor Google Earth)

Case Study	Data Source	Hollow Ways (estimated total length, m)
Northern Syria	Corona 1967	29,101
	Corona 1968	104,946
	Google Earth, 2004–2024	50,798
Southern Iraq	Corona 1968	181,284
	Google Earth, 2009–2024	78,436
Southern Ukraine	Hexagon 1972	18,385
	Google Earth, 2004–2022	17,040

Fig. 3. An example of selecting hollow ways that appear in one dataset (blue, historic Corona imagery), but not in the other (red). Due to errors in the process, discussed in the text, resulting values only provide an approximation of the true value and should only be seen as general estimates

Fig. 4. The southern Ukraine area of interest in the region of the Karachekrak River crossings with hollow ways mapped from satellite imagery (Background: ESRI World Hillshade)

Fig. 5. Visual comparison of the two datasets produced from historic imagery and very high-resolution imagery available in Google Earth reveals that while some hollow ways are detected in both sources, unique hollow ways are detected in each data source

Discussion

Some of the hollow ways found uniquely in the historic imagery may no longer be preserved in the modern landscape recorded by very high-resolution satellite imagery. Likewise, some of the hollow ways found uniquely in Google Earth may post-date historic imagery, however, the case study area within southern Ukraine does not correspond to a living landscape of actively used mounds and settlements. Likewise, many of the sites with the area of interest in southern Iraq have been abandoned for decades or longer (Jotheri et al., 2019).

It is known in archaeological remote sensing generally that various factors can impact visibility within any single image containing only visible bands of light, such as the satellite imagery used in this study. These include: the presence or absence of clouds, presence or absence of vegetation, soil moisture levels, and properties related to moisture evaporation from the ground (Altaweel, 2005; Stone & Zimansky, 2004; Wilkinson, 2003). The historic satellite imagery selected for this study did not have clouds over the areas of interest, but clouds were present in some of the very high-resolution satellite imagery available on Google Earth.

Among the Google Earth imagery available for the northern Syrian case study area, the images collected in December were often better than other images. This is likely due to the relatively high level of moisture present in the landscape following the start of the rainy season around October. In an arid environment, the collection of moisture in the depression of the hollow ways would make them appear more prominent. Generally, this principle would also be expected in Iraq, but in the southern Iraq case study area, it was images from 22 April 2019 and August 2018 that were among the better images. Both dates correspond to periods when the landscape is drying out: in April at the end of the rainy season and in August when desiccation of the marshes is maximal towards the end of the dry season. The relatively clear appearance of archaeological features, including subsurface features, at the end of a rainy season when the previously saturated ground is drying in southern Iraq has already been observed in the context of building footprints that suddenly appear very clearly on the surface of a site (Stone & Zimansky, 2004). The possibility to view multiple images from multiple times of year, including when soil moisture conditions could be ideal for mapping archaeological features, is likely responsible for the majority of hollow ways in both northern Syria and southern Iraq that were only detected in very high-resolution imagery in Google Earth.

In southern Ukraine, variations in vegetation (new growth, long grass/hay) was the main factor affecting the visibility of hollow ways in both the historic imagery and the collection of very high-resolution imagery available in Google Earth.

Nonetheless, the impact of ploughing and development on the preservation and visibility of hollow ways is evident if comparing historic imagery to more recent, very high-resolution imagery. The effects of these activities on the hollow ways of northern Syria, among other processes, have been described in detail elsewhere (de Gruchy & Cunliffe, 2020, pp. 130–140). In southern Ukraine, mapping of hollow ways was negatively impacted by areas of intensified ploughing, expansion of irrigation systems, and the construction of new buildings. In particular, a significant portion of the visible surface has been lost due to urban development in Vasylivka and surrounding villages.

Conclusions

Across the three case study regions, each source of imagery provides unique data for documenting ancient and historic movement as evidenced by hollow ways. While a single, historic Corona or Hexagon image allows a researcher to identify and document at least as much of the landscape of movement evidenced by hollow ways as the entire, combined volume of very high-resolution satellite imagery available on Google Earth; many lengths of hollow ways are only visible in one dataset or another – not both.

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